

An Equation for Variation of Viscosity with Temperature

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A modified equation representing the variation of viscosity with temperature over high as well as low temperature regions has been suggested. Calculations have been done for Aniline and Chlorobenzene.

BATCHINSKI¹ and Hildebrand² suggested a linear relationship between fluidity ϕ and molar volume V in the form $\phi = B(V - V_0)/V_0$, where V_0 is the molar volume at which viscous flow ceases and B is a constant. Eicher and Zwolenski³ and later Ertl and Dullien⁴ pointed out that while this equation is satisfactory in the 'high' temperature region, at 'low' temperature, i.e., for $T/T_c \leq 0.46$ (T_c being the critical temperature), is larger than that predicted by the linear relation. The viscosity data in the low temperature region may be represented by a polynomial relationship between viscosity and molar volume, but such an equation will not hold in the high temperature region.

In the present attempt a semi-empirical equation has been obtained by adding a suitable 'correction' term to the commonly used linear relation and may be written as

$$\phi = z + K e^{-x} z^n \quad \dots (1)$$

where $c_1 x = c_1 x + c_2 \quad \dots (2)$

Here x represents $(V - V_0)$, where V is the molar volume at the given temperature and V_0 is the molar volume at the freezing point, which is calculated using the extrapolated value of density. The constants c_1 , c_2 , K and n are characteristic of the liquid chosen. The correction term ($K e^{-x} z^n$) may be regarded as correlated to the 'pre-freezing' effect discussed by Ubbelohde and co-workers⁵ and is found to become significant at low temperature and negligible in the high temperature region.

The constants c_1 and c_2 in eq. (1) may be determined by using standard linear regression technique taking the viscosity data in the high temperature region only and assuming that the correction term is negligible in this region. This assumption is justified by the results obtained in the end. In order to determine the remaining two constants K and n , we write eq. (1) as

$$[\ln(\phi - z) + x] = n(\ln z) - \ln K \quad \dots (3)$$

and perform linear regression calculations using the new variables and making use of the data in the low

temperature region. Calculations were done for the two liquids Chlorobenzene and Aniline, whose viscosity^{6,7,9} and density⁸ data are easily available in the low as well as high temperature regions. For making least square fit, the boundary between the two regions was taken at 0° for Chlorobenzene and at 40° for Aniline. This choice is, however, relevant to the available data only and is by no means unique. The values of constants determined in this way are given in Table 1, which also lists the freezing points and the V_0 values.

TABLE-1

System	c_1	c_2	K	n	Freezing point(°C)	V_0 (cm ³ /mol)
Chlorobenzene	0.165	0.242	1.012	1.500	-45.2	89.187
Aniline	0.151	0.119	0.373	0.066	-6.1	95.604

TABLE 2

COMPARISON OF EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED VALUES OF FLUIDITY, (CP⁻¹)

Temp.	Chlorobenzene ^{6,9}		Temp.	Aniline ⁷	
	Experimental	Calculated		Experimental	Calculated
-45	0.376	0.362	5	0.124	0.122
-41	0.421	0.419	10	0.153	0.156
-38	0.454	0.467	15	0.188	0.187
-34	0.501	0.504	20	0.227	0.225
-30	0.546	0.551	25	0.269	0.269
-26	0.600	0.598	30	0.316	0.318
-20	0.685	0.672	35	0.369	0.370
-10	0.801	0.803	40	0.422	0.422
0	0.950	0.947	50	0.540	0.542
4.7	1.012	1.017	60	0.662	0.665
9.7	1.091	1.093	70	0.787	0.791
15.9	1.179	1.190	80	0.917	0.922
17.6	1.209	1.217	90	1.069	1.056
20.1	1.250	1.257	Standard deviation = 0.005		
25.1	1.332	1.338			
30.2	1.420	1.422			
40.2	1.590	1.591			
49.9	1.754	1.760			
60.0	1.949	1.940			
72.1	2.174	2.163			
Standard deviation = 0.007					

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Comprison of the experimental and calculated values (Table 2) shows that the standard deviations are quite low and individual deviations do not exceed two per cent. for both the liquids except for the single temperature of 45°, which is very near the freezing point of Chlorobenzene and where the deviation is expected to be large. In the case of Aniline, calculations could not be carried out near the freezing point since the negative value of constant c_2 makes the variable z turn negative near the freezing point. This, however, does not detract from the validity of eq. (1) over the rest of the region.

Thus it is found that the proposed eq. gives a good agreement between the experimental and calculated values of fluidity over comparatively wide temperature range, which extends below the transition temperature of $T/T_c \leq 0.46$. However very near the freezing points of the liquids, the equation does not give acceptable results, which is only to be expected.

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